

Notes on Four Sources Cited in “*The Application of Latent Semantic Analysis to the Voynich Manuscript*” by Layfield and Davis (2026)

Torsten Timm

ARTICLE HISTORY

Compiled May 28, 2026

ABSTRACT

Layfield and Davis (2026) apply Latent Semantic Analysis to the Voynich Manuscript and engage with a substantial prior literature on the manuscript’s two Currier languages, A and B. This note documents four places where the paper’s characterization of cited sources does not match what those sources say. In one case, the cited classifications differ from the citing paper’s representation of them, and the cited author’s disclaimers about the labels are not carried into the citing paper. In another, the cited paper’s terminology is attributed from a different paper, and the cited paper’s own contribution on the same question is not represented. In a third, the cited paper does not address the topic of the citation. In the fourth, the cited paper draws the opposite conclusion from the one it is cited to support. Each can be verified directly by readers consulting the cited works.

1. Introduction

Layfield and Davis (2026) apply Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) to the Voynich Manuscript and engage with a substantial prior literature on the manuscript’s two “Currier languages,” A and B. In the course of working through that literature for an unrelated project, the present author encountered several places where the paper’s characterization of cited sources does not match what those sources say. This short note documents four such cases, with the relevant passages quoted from both the citing paper and the cited works so that readers can verify each claim directly.

The note is descriptive rather than evaluative. It makes no argument about the paper’s broader conclusions; its purpose is solely to put on record four specific places where the cited literature does not authorize what the citation is used to assert. Each can be checked in minutes by anyone with the cited papers in hand. There is no objection in principle to any of the paper’s substantive conclusions; the present note concerns sources and citations only.

It should be noted at the outset that the present author is the corresponding author of one of the four sources discussed below (Case 2). The case is included here because the citation-accuracy issue is of the same kind as the others, and a note that addressed three third-party cases while staying silent on a parallel case involving the author’s own work would be incomplete. Readers should treat Case 2 with appropriate awareness that it directly involves the present author; the documentary verifications

are nonetheless straightforward.

2. Case 1: Currier’s section classifications and Table 1

Table 1 of Layfield and Davis (2026) (“Summary of the Voynich Manuscript”), reproduced in part here as Table 1, assigns the manuscript’s sections, scribes, and Currier languages.

Table 1. Sections, scribes, and Currier languages, reproduced from Table 1 of Layfield and Davis (2026). The original includes a Quire Structure column, omitted here.

Section	Scribe(s)	Languages
Botanical (ff. 1r–66v)	1, 2, 3, 5	A, B
Cosmological/Astronomical/Astrological diagrams (ff. 67r–74v)	4	B
Biological (ff. 75r–84v)	2	B
Rose foldout (ff. 85r–86v)	2, 4	B
Pharmaceutical/Recipes (ff. 87r–102v)	1, 3	A, B
Stars (ff. 103r–116r)	3, 2	B

The Currier source for these classifications, originally circulated as part of the 1976 NSA seminar proceedings and declassified in 2017 (Currier, 1976), gives the section-level language assignments differently in two places. From Currier’s Appendix A, paragraph 1(a), on the *Astrological Section*:¹

“there seemed to be no significant difference in the writing on any of the folios... The language throughout is mostly A but without some of the more pronounced A features found in Herbal A.”

From Currier’s Appendix A, paragraph 1(d), on the *Recipe Section* (pp. 212–234, corresponding to folios 103–116):

“The language throughout the Section is modified B (i.e., contains certain A characteristics).”

Table 1 of Layfield and Davis (2026) classifies the Cosmological/Astronomical/Astrological diagrams section (ff. 67r–74v)—the same group of folios—as pure Language B, where Currier classifies it as mostly A. Table 1 classifies the Stars section (ff. 103r–116r) as pure B, where Currier classifies the analogous Recipe Section as modified B containing A characteristics. The two intermediate classifications in Currier (mostly-A, modified-B-with-A) are not represented in the table; both are collapsed to pure B.

The “isomorphism” between Davis (2020)’s scribal hands and Currier’s languages—namely “*Scribe 1 writes entirely in Language A while Scribes 2, 3, 4, and 5 use Language B*”—was inherited from Bower and Lindemann (2021), where it is described as an isomorphism between Davis (2020) and Currier (1976). That isomorphism holds

¹Currier specifies the section as “pp 113–146.” In Currier’s pagination this nominally covers folios 58–74; folios 59–64 were already missing at the time of his analysis. The physically extant folios in this range are f58, f65, f66, and Quires 9–12 (f67–f74). Currier’s own foliation-pagination concordance (Table A) classifies f58 as Language A and f66 as Language B, which is incompatible with the “mostly A” summary of the Astrological Section. The most coherent reading is that Currier’s analytical object in this passage is Quires 9–12 (f67r–f74v)—the cosmological/astronomical/astrological group that Layfield and Davis’s Table 1 also treats as a section—with the f58/f65/f66 folios included in the page-range specification through a slight extension across the Quire 8 boundary.

against Davis (2020) but not directly against Currier (1976), who identifies “*perhaps as many as eight or a dozen different identifiable hands*” across only two languages—substantially more hands than the five-scribe model assigns. Currier’s hand-count and his gradient language classifications were both load-bearing in his original analysis. Neither appears in the Table 1 representation of his work.

Additionally, Currier explicitly cautions throughout his text that the term “language” is being used in a loose, statistical sense and “*in no way implies the existence of any underlying language*”—a disclaimer that bears on how the A/B distinction can be invoked in arguments about textual content. The disclaimer is absent from Layfield and Davis (2026).

3. Case 2: Timm and Schinner (2020, 2024) and the “gradual evolution” attribution

Layfield and Davis (2026), in their literature-review section, write: “[Timm and Schinner 2023] performed several experiments on the Voynich Manuscript in order to ascertain how related or unrelated the Currier ‘Language A’ and ‘Language B’ variants might be. . . They concluded there is no sudden transition between the two ‘languages,’ A and B, and that there is a gradual evolution between them after experimenting with cosine calculations between all possible pairs of pages.”

The cited paper is Timm and Schinner (2024)². The paper does not use the term “gradual.” On the question of A/B membership it argues:

“The answer to the question of whether a particular folio would belong to Currier A is not a definitive yes or no, but rather a percentage number.”

Where the paper refers to the gradual-evolution interpretation, it explicitly refers back to the earlier 2020 paper:

“This behavior confirms the hypothesis of a continuous evolution from Currier A to B, which had been derived previously [28] on the basis of token/word statistics.”

The “gradual evolution” terminology appears in the earlier paper, Timm and Schinner (2020), where the argument is made on the basis of token-frequency statistics:

“reordering the sections with respect to the frequency of token <chedy> replaces the seemingly irregular mixture of two separate languages by the gradual evolution of a single system from ‘state A’ to ‘state B’.”

The argument is licensed by the asymmetric containment principle (“*Since words typical for Currier A also exist in Currier B, but not the other way round*”) and supported by Table 2 of the 2020 paper, which displays the section-by-section frequency gradient for the token <chedy> and related items.

So the “gradual evolution” conclusion attributed by Layfield and Davis to the 2024 paper is in fact a result of the 2020 paper, with the 2024 paper referring back to it. The actual contribution of the 2024 paper on this question—A/B membership modeled as a percentage rather than a definitive assignment—is not represented in Layfield and Davis (2026). The cosine experiments described in the 2024 paper produce the evidence base (the smooth descending similarity curve over 5,151 folio-pair vectors, Figure 1 of the 2024 paper) for the continuous-evolution claim that was originally made in 2020.

²Layfield and Davis (2026) refer to this paper as “Timm and Schinner 2023,” reflecting the year embedded in the DOI prefix. The paper was published in *Cryptologia* Vol. 48, Issue 4, in 2024. The present note uses the publication year throughout.

4. Case 3: Lindemann and Bower (2021) and the LSA / polysemy / homophony citation

Layfield and Davis (2026), in their discussion of Sterneck et al. (2021), characterize Latent Semantic Analysis as “a technique that does not perform well with polysemy or homophony as such relationships dilute the method’s ability to discover underlying latent connections between word usage” and immediately add: “Entropy experiments in [Lindemann and Bower 2021] suggest this may be an issue.”

Lindemann and Bower (2021), “Character Entropy in Modern and Historical Texts: Comparison Metrics for an Undeciphered Manuscript” (arXiv:2010.14697v2), does not address this question. A full-text string search of the paper returns zero occurrences of the terms “polysemy,” “homophony,” and “LSA”. The paper’s empirical subject is conditional character entropy (h_2)—the predictability of the next character given the previous—across three corpora (Voynich texts, 311 Wikipedia language samples, and 18 historical manuscript samples). This is a character-level statistical property; it does not bear on the behavior of LSA, on word-sense ambiguity in topic-modeling pipelines, or on the question Layfield and Davis invoke the citation to support.

The substantive observation about LSA’s behavior with polysemous or homophonous words is a generic point in the natural-language processing literature and may not require Voynich-specific support at all. But if Voynich-specific support is to be cited, Lindemann and Bower (2021) does not provide it. The paper that does engage LSA in a Voynich context, Sterneck et al. (2021), is cited in the same paragraph; their decision to move from LSA to non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) is explained in their own paper and would be the appropriate reference.

5. Case 4: Lindemann and Bower (2021) and the A/B distinction

In their Conclusion, Layfield and Davis (2026) write: “Languages A and B, on the other hand, are shown to display a surprising degree of dissimilarity, a result that directly contrasts with some research in this area but that supports other results [Lindemann and Bower 2021].”

The actual finding on the A/B distinction is the opposite. Lindemann and Bower (2021), in section 4.3.2 (“Languages A and B”), opens:

Voynich Language A and Language B are similar at the character level. Despite the fact that they have different distributions at the word level, the most frequent character sequences are roughly the same in both languages.

The paper then identifies two specific exceptions—the word-final sequence <-edy> (approximately 86 times more frequent in B than in A) and the word-initial sequence <qo-> (approximately twice as frequent in B)—and reports:

If the two sequences are removed from both texts, then the h_2 value for Language A and Language B come within about 1% of each other.

Lindemann and Bower (2021) report a reducibility of the A/B difference to two specific affixes, with the underlying structure characterized as similar. Layfield and Davis (2026) invoke this work as supporting a “surprising degree of dissimilarity.” The cited work characterizes the difference as the opposite. The paper does not support the claim attributed to it.

6. Conclusion

The four cases mentioned have something in common: the actual statement in the cited source does not correspond to how it is used in the citing paper.

In Case 1, the cited classifications differ from the citing paper’s representation of them, and the cited author’s disclaimers about the labels are not carried into the citing paper.

In Case 2, the cited paper’s terminology is attributed from a different paper, and the cited paper’s own contribution on the same question is not represented.

In Case 3, the cited paper does not address the topic of the citation.

In Case 4, the cited paper draws the opposite conclusion from the one it is cited to support.

Each of the four cases has another characteristic in common: a direct quotation from the cited source would have made the discrepancy immediately visible. The Voynich literature is small, the cited works are short, and the relevant passages are easy to locate. The four cases are documented here without further comment. Each can be verified directly by readers consulting the cited works, and corrected easily in any subsequent erratum or revised version. The broader interpretive questions raised by Layfield and Davis (2026) are not addressed here.

References

- Bowern, C. L., and Lindemann, L. (2021). The linguistics of the Voynich manuscript. *Annual Review of Linguistics*, 7, 285–308. doi:10.1146/annurev-linguistics-011619-030613
- Currier, P. H. (1976). New research on the Voynich Manuscript. In M. E. D’Imperio (Ed.), *Proceedings of a Seminar, 30 November 1976*. Washington, DC: NSA (declassified 18 July 2017, FOIA Case 101982). <https://media.defense.gov/2021/Jul/13/2002761428/-1/-1/0/PROCEEDINGS-OF-A-SEMINAR-30-NOVEMBER-1976.PDF> (accessed May 25, 2026). A transcription by J. Guy and J. Reeds (1992) is available at https://www.voynich.nu/extra/curr_main.html.
- Davis, L. F. (2020). How many glyphs and how many scribes? Digital paleography and the Voynich Manuscript. *Journal for Manuscript Studies*, 5(1), 164–180.
- Layfield, C., and Davis, L. F. (2026). The Application of Latent Semantic Analysis to the Voynich Manuscript. *Digital Humanities Quarterly*, 20(1). doi:10.63744/2ezxpskcezq4
- Lindemann, L., and Bowern, C. (2021). Character entropy in modern and historical texts: Comparison metrics for an undeciphered manuscript. *arXiv:2010.14697v2*. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2010.14697
- Sterneck, R., Polish, A., and Bowern, C. (2021). Topic modeling in the Voynich Manuscript. *arXiv:2107.02858*. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2107.02858
- Timm, T., and Schinner, A. (2020). A possible generating algorithm of the Voynich manuscript. *Cryptologia*, 44(1), 1–19. doi:10.1080/01611194.2019.1596999
- Timm, T., and Schinner, A. (2024). The Voynich manuscript: Discussion of text creation hypotheses. *Cryptologia*, 48(4), 305–322. doi:10.1080/01611194.2023.2225716